

FEATURES OF THE CLINICAL COURSE OF FACIAL NERVE NEUROPATHY DEPENDING ON GENDER AND AGE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8398090>

ANNOTATION The study showed that facial nerve neuropathies (FN) have specific clinical course and are manifested predominantly by right-sided lesions of the facial nerve in females. The idiopathic form of NLN reliably prevails among young people, while other forms, in particular vascular LLN, are found mainly in old age. Symptomatic forms of NLN, arising from diseases of the ENT organs, as well as vascular and inflammatory etiologies, have more severe motor disorders and are characterized by poor recovery of impaired functions compared to the idiopathic form of LLN.

Keywords: acute neuropathy of the facial nerve, age, gender, clinical and pathogenetic features.

Introduction. Facial nerve neuropathy (FN) is a disease that is one of the most common cranial neuropathies, the frequency of which in adults is 12-26 cases per 100 thousand population or 2-5% of all diseases of the peripheral nervous system of inflammatory origin. Despite a large number of studies, questions regarding the characteristics of the clinical course of facial nerve neuropathy depending on age remain unresolved. It has now been proven that the causes of the disease can be middle ear infections, sinusitis, mumps, trauma, neoplasms, demyelinating diseases of the central nervous system, and the consequences of surgical interventions. The facial nerve is one of the youngest cranial nerves and is therefore easily vulnerable. Young, that is, one of the last to appear in the history of the development of living organisms. Animals already have it, but practically do not bear any loads. Among people, it plays one of the main roles. The main activity of the nerve is the innervation of facial muscles: we owe it the ability to smile and frown, raise our eyebrows in surprise and wrinkle our nose.

Purpose of the study: to study the clinical and pathogenetic features of acute NLN depending on sexual dimorphism and age of patients.

Materials and methods. The study was conducted on the material of the regional multidisciplinary medical center of Urgench, where for the period 2020–2022. 50 patients with acute LFN were examined and treated. Of the above number of patients, in 27 (54%) cases these were male patients, and in 23 (46%) - female patients, who were divided into two groups based on gender. Patients included in the study were recruited randomly. In addition to studying complaints and the clinical picture of the disease, all patients underwent a general clinical and neurological examination, neuroimaging (magnetic resonance imaging and multislice computed tomography), electroneuromyography (ENMG) and laboratory examination. Acute LLN had right-sided lateralization in 33 cases, and left-sided lateralization in 17 cases. During a neurological examination of patients,

Results.In the structure of acute lesions of LN, the idiopathic form of LN significantly predominates. With this form of LN, the right LN is more often affected, especially in the group of female patients. Anamnestic data collected from this group of patients showed that in the absolute number of patients (33 (66%)) the provoking factor of the disease was hypothermia. The maximum number of patients with the idiopathic form of NLN occurs among young people, while in average and especially in old age this form is observed less frequently. Thus, at a young age, colds and exposure to cold play a major role in the development of NLN, since patients lead a more active lifestyle. And this form was characterized by the development of the disease in the cool seasons of the year. Vascular forms of damage to the facial nerve were observed with a slight advantage in frequency in males compared to females. In this form of NLN, we did not observe a clear sign of predominant lateralization. The role of vascular factors in FN damage was evidenced by a history of hypertensive crisis, widespread cerebral atherosclerosis and diabetic micro- and macroangiopathy. The patients were middle-aged and elderly, suffering from hypertension, atherosclerosis, and type II diabetes mellitus. Cases of otogenic lesions of the FN had no sign of predominant lateralization and strictly coincided with the side of inflammation. A feature of the neurological picture of otogenic FLN is the development of signs of damage to the FL in its tympanic and mastoid regions. In the patients we observed with vascular forms of NLN, in 15 cases (70%) the patients were elderly, in 8 cases (24%) they were middle-aged. In 7 cases, acute PD developed against the background of a hypertensive crisis, in 6 cases - against the background of a combination of atherosclerosis and arterial hypertension. 5 patients had progressive diabetic micro- and macroangiopathy, confirmed by the clinical picture and instrumental studies. Thus, the importance of the vascular factor NLN begins to prevail with age and an increase in systemic vascular pathology. 5 patients had progressive diabetic micro- and macroangiopathy, confirmed by the clinical picture and instrumental studies. Thus, the importance of the vascular factor NLN begins to prevail with age and an increase in systemic vascular pathology. 5 patients had progressive diabetic micro- and macroangiopathy, confirmed by the clinical picture and instrumental studies. Thus, the importance of the vascular factor NLN begins to prevail with age and an increase in systemic vascular pathology.

Discussion.Diseases of the ENT organs, in particular purulent otitis media, mastoiditis, as causes of secondary NLN, were almost uniformly observed in all age groups, but more often in females. It was noteworthy that, despite radical operations, the manifestations of NLN were crude and persistent. Thus, according to the results of the study, the dynamics of additional symptoms of PD have certain gender differences. If xerostomia, hypogeusia, pain, hyperacusis, lacrimation, xerophthalmia in the acute period of the disease in terms of frequency of manifestation have a similar picture among males and females, then in subsequent periods of the disease significant differences in many symptoms are observed. For example, pain syndrome and xerostomia in the early period of recovery of LLN in male patients had significantly better regression compared to female patients. The fastest recovery of lacrimation is observed after the early recovery period, that is, during the late recovery period. The most persistent and severe symptom of NLN is xerophthalmia, which is more persistent in men, but is twice as common in female patients.

Conclusions.NLN have gender differences and manifests itself as a predominant right-sided lesion of the facial nerve in females. The idiopathic form of NLN reliably prevails among young people, while other forms, in particular vascular LLN, are observed mainly in old age.

Symptomatic forms of NLN, arising from diseases of the ENT organs, as well as vascular and inflammatory etiologies, have more severe motor disorders and are characterized by poor recovery compared to the idiopathic form of LLN.

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